

Publication Identifiers

A decision tree to distinguish between the different types of publication identifier to use for different types of published content such as journal articles, books, conference proceedings. The tree covers various considerations which were identified by FREYA partners as affecting their choice of identifier. Some identifiers are suitable for more than one purpose and some identifiers can be implemented in a very similar way and have similar coverage therefore some of these options appear more than once.

Why do you want a publication identifier?

Publication Identifiers

A decision tree to distinguish between the different types of publication identifier to use for different types of published content such as journal articles, books, conference proceedings. The tree covers various considerations which were identified by FREYA partners as affecting their choice of identifier. Some identifiers are suitable for more than one purpose and some identifiers can be implemented in a very similar way and have similar coverage therefore some of these options appear more than once.

DOI €

A Digital Object Identifier is a persistent identifier using the Handle system and is used to identify objects, based on an ISO standard. The developer and administrator of the DOIs is the International DOI Foundation (IDF). The DOI system is implemented through a federation of registration agencies, such as DataCite and Crossref, coordinated by the IDF. DataCite is a membership organization which provides services to create, find, cite, connect, and use datasets and other research objects. Crossref is a membership organization which provides content registration services to assign DOIs and register metadata for journal articles, books, conference proceedings and preprints.

Format: <https://doi.org/10.8080/123456>

Wikidata item

Wikidata is a central storage repository that can be accessed by others, such as the wikis maintained by the Wikimedia foundation.

The Wikidata repository consists mainly of items, each one having a label, a description and any number of aliases. Items are uniquely identified by a Q followed by a number.

Format: [Q821542](https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q821542)

ISBN €

The International Standard Book Number is a numeric commercial book identifier which is intended to be unique. Publishers purchase ISBNs from an affiliate of the International ISBN Agency. An ISBN is assigned to each separate edition and variation of a publication.

Format: [978-3-16-148410-0](https://www.isbn-international.org/en/978-3-16-148410-0)

Discipline-specific identifier

Some academic disciplines have their own discipline-specific identifiers. For example:

- bibcode/refcode in astronomy which is used by some astronomical data systems to specify literature references.

Format: [1924MNRAS..84..308E](https://ui.adsabs.org/abs/1992MNRAS...84..308E)

- PMID is the unique identifier number used in PubMed. They are automatically assigned to each article record when it enters the PubMed system.

Format: [32335169](https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/32335169/)

Handle

The Handle system (www.handle.net) was developed by Corporation for National Research Initiatives (CNRI). It is a framework for managing digital information and provides a naming scheme for unique identifiers, called 'Handles'. A resolution system translates the handles into location-related data. A centrally administered registry service manages the resolving naming authorities. A Handle consists of two parts: a naming authority and a unique string that identifies an object. The ePIC consortium provides PID services for the European research community for the allocation and resolution of persistent identifiers.

Format: [11304/69544d65-3ef6-45ca-84a6-04152313872e](https://www.handle.net/11304/69544d65-3ef6-45ca-84a6-04152313872e)

ISSN €

ISSN stands for International Standard Serial Number. An ISSN's role is to identify a publication and is linked to the title of a publication. It can be used for print or online materials such as proceedings, journal articles and blogs. In many countries, an ISSN is mandatory for all publications subject to the legal deposit. The ISSN portal <http://portal.issn.org/> provides free metadata which is sufficient to identify titles and which is human and machine readable. ISSN is interoperable and can cross check metadata with Wikidata and Crossref metadata. All ISSNs are embedded in URIs with the format <https://portal.issn.org/resource/ISSN/0986-6751>

Format: [ISSN 0986-6751](https://portal.issn.org/resource/ISSN/0986-6751)

arXiv identifier

arXiv is an open access repository of electronic preprints (known as e-prints), predominantly in the fields of mathematics and physics. Each e-print posted on arXiv receives an arXiv ID.

Format (from 2015): [YYMM/NNNNN \(English\)](https://arxiv.org/abs/1501.00001)

€ Membership/Subscription Fees

All services with this symbol charge some sort of membership or subscription fee for full access to the service. Full access can include features such as minting the PIDs and API access. These fees can vary depending on the service and the type of organisation who wishes to use them. Many of the PID services which do not have membership or subscription fees require more technical resources from your organisation to set up and maintain the service.

For more information on Publication Identifiers

- FREYA Knowledge Hub page on Identifiers for Publications and Data <https://www.pidforum.org/t/pids-forpublications-and-data/297>
- D3.1 Survey of Current PID Services Landscape <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3554254>

Copyright of Members of the FREYA Consortium. Created by members of the FREYA Consortium. This work is made available under a Creative Commons CC BY License <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>
The FREYA project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 777523.